

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NATURAL
ANTIMICROBIALS ON SHELF-LIFE & FOODBORNE
PATHOGENS WITH RESPECT TO CONSUMER DEMAND**¹Dr. Anum Waqar, ²Dr. Amna Anam, ²Dr. Rabia Abid¹Jinnah Hospital²Mayo Hospital**Abstract**

In the emerging demand of consumers for multi-drug resistance in foodborne pathogens for less processed but fresh food; the food industry is striving for more natural antimicrobials. Taste and flavour are being increased through plants. With all other added factors and properties, essential oils and extracts act as antimicrobials and antioxidants without harming the overall food quality. In this perspective, we studied and reviewed essential oils and natural extracts in the context of their effectiveness against shelf life extension, foodborne pathogens and spoilage microorganism.

Keywords: *Food Preservation, Food Spoilage, Natural Antimicrobial and Food Pathogens.*

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Please cite this article in press Anum Waqar et al., Assessment Of The Effectiveness Of Natural Antimicrobials On Shelf-Life & Foodborne Pathogens With Respect To Consumer Demand., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

In the emerging demand of consumers for multi-drug resistance in foodborne pathogens for less processed but fresh food; the food industry is striving for more natural antimicrobials. A lot of attention has been diverted towards the use of essential oils and plant extracts in order to gain flavour, anti-microbial activities and antioxidant [1]. A range of animals and plants was also assessed for food system [2]. These authors consider the role of natural anti-microbial scan as an important element. Prakash assessed a variety of fruits such as Orange, Papaya, Banana etc. for the determination of antimicrobial activity and concluded that these fruits contain moderate to mild pathogenic bacteria inhibiting effect [3]. We have discussed these effective elements in detail in this review.

RECENT WORKS ON NATURAL ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTIVENESS IN FOODS SYSTEMS IN PAKISTAN:

The juice, extracts, paste, oils and powders are utilized for the assessment of antimicrobial and antioxidant effect against numerous shelf life and foodborne pathogens [4]. Numerous authors have studied various aspects of antimicrobial activity among numerous phenolic substances and extracted materials from plants for shortlisted microbes. Quercetin, Naringenin and Flavone had effective outcomes in the inhibition of an organism's growth. Few of the other authors have also reported the effectiveness of the basil oil, leucas extract and other plants such as Anethum graveolens, Cuminum cyminum etc [5]. with differing sensitivities. The effectiveness of various other extracts of grape seed, aqueous, ethanolic, Punica granatum, Hedychium larsenii M rhizomes oil, Seabuckthorn, Bacillus cereus, Bacillus subtilis, Staphylococcus aureus, Enterococcus faecalis, Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumonia, Ravinia sp, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Proteus Vulgaris, Blumea lacera, Canscora diffuse, Cassia alata, fistula L, C. Biflora L, Putranji varoxburghii Wall etc had varying effectiveness against gram negative and gram positive bacteria as reported by various authors in different research series [6 – 8]. There is a long list to of various effective extracts along with the few mentioned with different effectiveness levels for antimicrobial activity. It was also revealed by various authors that extracts of plants are less active to gram-negative than gram-positive bacteria. According to Chauhan, there is an antibacterial activity in the extracts of Seabuckthorn seeds aqueous against Yersinia enterocolitica and Listeria monocytogenes which implicates natural preservation of the extracts [9]. In

the recent developments, the use of garlic and ginger essential oils has produced promising outcomes against E. coli, Staphylococcal counts and Salmonella. Upadhyay reported growth inhibiting outcomes of the extracts of hydroalcoholic and aqueous against Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Bacillus cereus, Enterococcus faecalis and Staphylococcus aureus. Chaudhary and Verma reported C. carandas fruits extracts and indicated anti-E. Coli antibacterial activity [10]. According to Arora sea buckthorn crude extracts possesses antibacterial properties for pomace, leaves against 17th foodborne pathogens and seeds [11]. Gupta assessed the outcomes of various tropical fruits against 4 gram-negative and 5 gram-positive bacteria [12]. In the long list of evaluated extracts for the best available antimicrobial activity, Artocarpus lachoocha and Carissa carandas had better outcomes. Kamaraj assessed leaf crude extracts for antibacterial properties among Aristolochia indica, Catharanthus roseus leaf, Cassia Angustifolia, Dolichos biflorus, Diospyros melanoxylon, Justicia procumbens and Gymnema Sylvestre against gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria along with E. Coli [13]. The inhibition zone was 20 mm against E. Coli for A. indica leaf methanol extract with an MIC value as (24.2 g/ml) leaf [14].

RECENT WORKS ON EFFECTIVENESS OF NATURAL ANTIMICROBIAL IN FOODS SYSTEMS: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE:

Majority of the work is carried out on the natural antimicrobial effectiveness; whereas, less attention is paid to the element of microorganism spoilage but there is a recent development in this area. However, there are various research studies on the effect of antioxidant are found with the use of juices, natural extracts, powder, pastes and oils in particular with the animal food origins [15]. Cutter experimented a series of research to find out the commercially available effectiveness in the general safer herbs against E. Coli, Listeria monocytogenes and Salmonella Typhimurium that had an association with beef [16]. It was suggested in the research that extracts of herbs can possible reduce the beef surface pathogens. A broader spectrum was assessed by Beg and Ahmad about the ethanolic extracts anti-microbial activity among 12 plants which include Eucalyptus sp, L. inermis, H. indicus, H. anti dysenterica, T. chebula, C. equistifolia. T. belerica, C.sinensis, E. officinalis, P. granatum and S. aromaticum against E. Coli, Salmonella paratyphi, Staphylococcus aureus, Bacillus subtilis, Shigella dysenteriae and Candida albicans (drug-resistant bacterias) [17 – 19]. Various other authors have also

reported the effectiveness of plants and flowers extracts such as *Limonium californicum*, *Cupressus Lusitania* Miller, *A. Heller*, *Jusiea peruviana* L and *Salvia Murcia* Epling which were effective for the inhibition of verotoxin production through enterohemorrhagic *E. Coli* [20]. Various oils and oil compounds were also effective against *E. Coli*, *Salmonellae Terica* and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Most effective oils against *E. Coli* include thyme, oregano, palmarosa, cinnamon, clove bud, bay leaf, allspice oils and lemongrass. Olasupo assessed the inhibition feature of various natural organic compounds alone and along with nisin combinations against *E. Coli*. Inhibition was available for two gram-negatives; whereas, no improvement was there with nisin combinations for the antimicrobial activity. Burt is of the view that essential oils antibacterial activity such as carvacrol, eugenol, thymol, cinnamaldehyde, perillaldehyde and cinnamic acid against gram negative and positive bacteria including *E. Coli* is between the levels of 0.2 & 10 micro ml (-1). The report of gram-negative organisms was slightly less in comparison to the gram-positive bacteria. Seventeen essential oils of plants were evaluated and nine compounds of oils by Friedman to assess the antibacterial activity against *E. Coli* (O157: H7) in the juice of apple; furthermore, he reported an activity against *E. Coli* in oregano oil, carvacrol, eugenol, geraniol, citral, cinnamon leaf oil, lemongrass oil, clove bud oil, lemon oil and cinnamon bark oil. Carvacrol was more effective than Citral [21]. Kim evaluated ten green leafy vegetables mostly consumed in the Eastern Asia countries against *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria mono cytogenes*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* with the help of broth microdilution tests and agar well diffusion [22]. In those, all green leafy vegetables chainmail and fatsia extracts possessed better antimicrobial features. Rounds also elaborated the effects of olive and apple extracts, clove bud oil and onion powder on *E. coli* (O157: H7). Extracts of Olive reduced *E. Coli* (O157: H7) at three percent; whereas, apple extract reduced up to 1 log [23].

4. CURRENT RESEARCH STUDIES ON THE PLANT EXTRACTS EFFECTIVENESS ON THE SHELF-LIFE AND FOODBORNE PATHOGENS

4.1. Pomegranate

Pomegranate extracts are also very much effective against numerous micro-organisms and also exhibit clear antimicrobial for *E. coli*; whereas, its ethanolic extract is very much effective against various enterohemorrhagic *E. Coli* (O157: H7) strains along with various other enterohemorrhagic *E. Coli* strains

[24]. Fawole experimented on seven samples of pomegranate which are grown commercially on gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria (*Klebsiella Pneumonia* and *Escherichia Coli*) [25]. The extract of methanolic peel reflected stronger and broader spectrum against gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria having reduced MIC in the range of (0.2 – 0.78) mg/ml. Tomasetti reported hot water sensitivity of *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella Typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, ethanol (95%) pomegranate fruit peels acetone extracts. The hot water peels extracts are more potent having reduced MIC against *E. Coli* (207 mg/ml) [26].

4.2. Citrus Fruits

Various authors have evaluated citrus fruits vapours and oils in order to evaluate an antimicrobial activity against a number of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms with specific reference to *E. Coli* as well. Better antimicrobial activity is present in the essential oils of bergamot, lemon and orange against *E. Coli* (O-157), *Listeria mono-cytogens*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Bacillus Cereus* [27]. Citrus crude extracts such as microcarpa showed a visible antimicrobial activity against seven reference bacterial strains which include *E. Coli* (ATCC-25922), *Aeromonas hydrophila* (ATCC-49140), *Citrobacter Freundii* (ATCC-8090), *Streptococcus Agalatae* (ATCC-13813), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC-35032), *Edward Siella Tarda* (ATCC-15947) and *Yersinia enterocolitica* (ATCC-23715) with a range of MIC values from 7.8 to 31.3 mg mL (-1) [28].

4.3. Ginger

Pakistani dishes include finger as a major element of numerous dishes as it possesses antioxidant and antimicrobial properties against *E. Coli*. An antimicrobial activity is also found in ginger against *E. Coli* (O157: H7); whereas, 70% ginger methanolic extract was also effective against *E. Coli* along with an MIC range of (50% – 90%) that equals 6.97 mg/ml. However, Goyal and Kaushik study organic extracts and crude aqueous of *Zingiber rhizome* (ginger) against *E. Coli*, they also suggested that organic extracts and methanolic crude display antibacterial effects but there was an in-effectivity of aqueous extracts. Pokhrel and Gull also study methanolic and ethanolic extracts along with various crude extracts and essential oils of ginger and reported different outcomes against 5 diarrhoea strains which caused *E. Coli*. They reported a susceptibility of these oils for *E. Coli*; whereas, not for the crude extracts [29].

4.4. Curry Leaves

Meethi Neem (*Murraya Koenigii* Linn) belongs to Rutaceae family. The tree of curry is easily available in Pakistan and neighbouring areas except for high mountain series. It is an effective anti-diabetic, antioxidant, antihypertensive, antibacterial, cytotoxic and it is also widely used to treat bronchial respiratory disorders. Curry leaves are primarily a part of various eatables and spices and its effect is studied for the foodborne pathogens by Malwal, Harika and Zachariah as it possesses enormous antimicrobial activity. Ningappa reported the monomeric protein isolated antibacterial activity from curry leaves. He further reports an effective inhibition of *E. Coli* with an MIC range of (13 – 24) µg/ml [30]. Baskaran observed that methanol, ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, petroleum ether, chloroform, aqueous and hexane curry leaves extracts to show an enormous antibacterial activity against Gram-negative and positive bacteria; whereas, *E. Coli* shows an increased susceptibility to acetone extract in the inhibition zone of (16.20 ± 0.20). Dichloro-methane soluble and Ethyl acetate of methanolic curry leaf extract exhibits a mild activity for *E. Coli* with a formation of inhibition zone of (9 – 11) mm.

4.5. Radish

Extracts of radish have also been under the assessment of various authors to indicate their antimicrobial activity for foodborne pathogens. These authors also reported the horseradish root extract antibacterial activity against *E. Coli* and an antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* which has reported food spoilage involvement. Beevi assessed hexane and acetone extracts which were taken from the leaf, root and stem of *Raphanus sativus* to find out the antibacterial activity against resistant and foodborne pathogens. Kumar used radish, coriander, curry and mint leave extracts to analyze the possible antimicrobial potential as he tested these extracts on various bacteria with the help of agar disc diffusion technique [31]. Janjua also analyzed various edible root peel extracts of *Raphanus Sativus* for any possible antibacterial activity against gram-negative and positive bacteria. Highest inhibition zone against *E. Coli* was (28 ± 1.2) mm for the extract of petroleum ether. They also told about the wastage of important *R. sativus* peels as it holds medicinal features [32].

4.6. Sea buckthorn

In the recently developed literature researchers have studied the extracts of sea buckthorn for shelf-life and foodborne pathogens. Dhanze reported sea buckthorn leaves aqueous extracts are significantly low (P-Value < 0.05) psychrophilic count (PC),

standard plate count (SPC), mould and yeast count (YMC) and coliform count (CC) on the leg of the chicken than controls [33]. While leaf extract of sea buckthorn (3%) treatment resulted with a significant (P-Value < 0.05) which reduced PC, SPC, YMC and CC within seven days. Another author reported the Sea buckthorn seed extracts for their antibacterial activity and reported the methanolic extract MIC values for *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus coagulans*, *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *Listeria monocytogenes* respectively 200, 300, 300, 350 and 300 ppm [34].

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of various research studied we conclude that there is antimicrobial activity within few extracts against various foodborne pathogens along with additional antimicrobial activity against a variety of microorganism's spoilage and the extended element of shelf-life. We can use these extracts alone as well as with the combination of other extracts in order to protect and preserve consumer food pathogens. We can also delay food spoilage as well.

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